

Creep Mechanisms of a Two-Phase, A2-B2 Superalloy

Supplementary Material

Liu Yang^{a1}, Aparajita Pramanik^{b1}, Sandipan Sen^{a*}, Shubhashis Dixit^a, Marcel Muench^a, R. J. Vikram^a, Daniel Schliephake^a, Yolita M. Eggeler^c, Ankur Chauhan^{b***}, Martin Heilmaier^a and Alexander Kauffmann^{d**}

^a Institute for Applied Materials (IAM-WK), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Engelbert-Arnold-Str. 4, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

^b Extreme Environments Materials Group (EEMG), Department of Materials Engineering, Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore, 560012, India

^c Laboratory for Electron Microscopy (LEM), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Engesserstr. 7, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

^d Institute for Materials (IM), Ruhr University Bochum (RUB), Universitätsstr. 150, 44801 Bochum, Germany

¹ equal contribution to the paper

corresponding authors

*mail: sandipan.sen@kit.edu (S. Sen)

**mail: alexander.kauffmann@rub.de (A. Kauffmann)

***mail: ankurchauhan@iisc.ac.in (A. Chauhan)

phone: +49 (0)234 32 18430

Figure S1. Inverse pole figure maps of (a) homogenized and furnace-cooled material, and samples crept at 1030 °C under an applied stress of (b) 100 MPa; (c) 125 MPa; and (d) 150 MPa.

Figure S2. (a) Grain boundary character map overlaid with IQ map of a smaller region of the sample crept at 100 MPa at 1030 °C and point to origin misorientation distribution across a representative; (b) high angle grain boundary (HAGB); (c) low angle grain boundary (LAGB); and (d) subgrain boundary formed during creep deformation (SGB).